

Equipment to monitor the pressure exerted on the feet of individuals with diabetic neuropathy: an architectural proposal for wireless communication and data transmission

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Abstract— Diabetic neuropathy is an aggravating condition of diabetes that affects many individuals with this disease worldwide. The various damages caused to health linked to the lack of resources to combat this condition highlight the importance of creating new mechanisms for this. Therefore, the main objective of this work is to address one of the most important factors in the conjuncture of an equipment project, consisting of two insoles with pressure sensors linked to an electrostimulator and the user's smartphone, which will be responsible for monitoring the health of people affected by the disease: wireless communication. This makes it possible to connect all the mechanisms that will be present in the project, exchanging information, commands and data processing. In this sense, one of the main aspects that constitute this information sharing is the network architecture, which involves a general characterization regarding communication, including aspects such as the protocols to be followed, the network topology, the composition of the nodes, among others; in addition to the transmission of data, which effectively sends and receives the desired information by the devices. Therefore, this work will essentially propose a network architecture model to underpin the monitoring equipment and will discuss the composition of the data transmission that will constitute the equipment system.

Keywords — *network architecture, network topology, data transmission, diabetic neuropathy*

I. Introduction

Diabetic neuropathy is a complication of diabetes that affects about 40% of patients aged 15 years or older with this disease, according to the National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases (NIDDK). In this regard, one of the main losses that affect people with this condition is the reduced sensitivity of their lower limbs, caused by damage to the individual's nervous system, in addition to the appearance of lesions in these places, which may go unnoticed by the person. This can pose a great risk to the patient, considering that wounds caused by diabetes can get worse due to the excess pressure generated at the site. This context, linked to the lack of resources to control and treat this disease, highlights the importance of this problem; which motivated the creation of a device to prevent further damage to the feet of individuals affected by the disease, through monitoring carried out by equipment consisting of insoles with pressure sensors, an electrostimulator and an application - all connected by a wireless network.

A wireless network is a communication system that allows

data transmission without the need for cables – this action is carried out by means of waves, in which the most used type is radiofrequency. This category is widely used, in a worldwide context, in applications that require sending and receiving data, mainly considering the practicality and effectiveness provided by this model by supporting the connection with multiple devices simultaneously. ment, with high transmission rates at high speed (according to the protocol followed) and without the demand for wires.

This communication is a fundamental element for the project: it will allow the exchange of information between the equipment components, such as sending data read by the pressure sensors in the insoles to the application and the control of the electrostimulator performed by the smartphone. In this sense, some of the main constituents of the desired type of information sharing concern the network's architecture – its organization, form, typology, protocol, and the nodes that make up this structure.

In this way, the main objective of this work is, in addition to discussing and studying the previously exposed topics, to propose an architecture model for wireless communication that fits all the components of the project in question (sensors, electrostimulator and smartphone), assign an analysis about the transmission of data via wireless and propose its constitution for the equipment.

II. Results and discussion

A. Network architecture

The architecture of a given wireless network provides an overview of this communication, determining a number of fundamental characteristics of the network, such as the hardware components used for communication, network topology, wireless connections, implemented areas, and software protocols. It is important to note that the nodes of a network are points of connections and can be an element of redistribution or a communication terminal.

In this sense, firstly, it is necessary to address the set of rules and standards to be properly followed to the implementation of the objectified project: the IEEE 802.15.6 protocol in conjunction with Wireless body area network (WBAN); this integration aims to provide a protocol with great adaptation to the international scenario, characterized by a short reach and high quality of service. The first regulation defines the physical layer (PHY) and the layer of access control to the media, Media Access Control (MAC) – assigning a comparison to the OSI model, it acts respectively on the physical and link layers; in addition, the standard typifies two operators in a network, which are the nodes: Full-Function Device (FFD), a component that

coordinates a network; and the Reduced-Function Device (RFD), a device with limited functions that communicates only with an FFD.

Next, it is necessary to elucidate on typologies. According to Dantas (2010, p. 197), "[...] topology can be understood as the manner in which communication links and switching devices are interconnected, effectively providing signal transmission between the nodes of the network"; in this respect, the protocol in question supports two types of topology: star and point-to-point. The main difference between such types is due to the fact that in the first, the information passes through a central station that will distribute traffic between secondary stations, not there is an exchange of data between the non-main points; while in the second type, there is a sharing of information between all nodes of the organization.

With regard to the WBAN network, it is widely used in the health context, in view of its great suitability to the applications of this environment, since it provides high reliability, reach in the area around the human body, low energy consumption and it supports various transmission rates.

Similar to RFD devices, in the WBAN system there is the sensor node; these sensor nodes are made up of three units: sensing, which is responsible for capturing the analog signals generated by the human body and transforming them into digital signals; the processing, which controls the activities of the node, such as data storage, its processing and the sending to the Transmission Unit; the Transmission Unit that transmits the data and receives confirmations.

After the brief explanation related to the architecture of a network, it is therefore appropriate to propose a possible organization model for the wireless communication of the objectified project. In this sense, the protocol to be followed is IEEE 802.15.6 and the WBAN network, in view of the aspects previously elucidated; the nodes of the structure are represented by the sensors of the insole, the electrostimulator and the smartphone, which, respectively, are characterized by RFD, RFD and FFD.

Thus, it is possible to infer that the topology of the star type would be the most appropriate, since in this structure, an FFD device centralizes and commands the communication flow, and there is no sharing among the other nodes. Thus, the coordinating node (center of the star) will be the smartphone, and the sensor nodes (tips of the stars) will be the sensors of the insoles and the electrostimulator, since the smartphone exchanges information with the other nodes (receiving data for reading and sending commands), and there is no need for sharing between the electrostimulator node and the sensor node; all this conjuncture is illustrated by Figure 1.

Fig. 1: proposed star-type architecture

With regard to the composition of the sensor nodes, firstly, in relation to the pressure sensor node, the sensing unit will be formed by the devices themselves, the processing unit by the ESP32 and the transmission unit will be constituted by the WiFi network created by this microcontroller (which will enable the exchange of information between the sensor node and the coordinator node); secondly, regarding the electrostimulator node, it will present a similar structure to the pressure sensors node, changing only the sensing node, which will be composed of the electrostimulator.

A fundamental part involving wireless network applications concerns the main factors that make up the transmission rate scenario, such as latency time, the maximum throughput of a sensor node and the maximum throughput of the network. In this sense, the first element is a measure of processing time between stimulus and response and indicates the access time to information in long-term memory (STERNBERG, 1992); its measurement for the intended project can be performed using a simple methodology, in which a GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) pin of a sensor node is configured as an input and a pin of the coordinator node is configured to be used as an output. Then these pins are connected, the sensor node sends a packet to the coordinator node (parameter 1); when effectively receiving the data, the output pin of the coordinator node has a high logic level; then the sensor node receives this logical high level from the coordinator node (parameter 2). The latency time is calculated as follows: latency time = parameter 1 – parameter 2.

With regard to the maximum transmission rate of a sensor node, which is related to the maximum data transfer to the coordinator node that a sensor node can perform, it can be calculated using only one sensor node. In this sense, according to (SILVA, 2022) you must repeatedly transmit packets with the payload (essential information) full (2312bytes) and increase the transmission frequency; thus, to find the communication limit between the sensor node and the coordinator node, just use the equation: transmission rate = number of packets received * 2312bytes * 8bits.

In relation to the maximum network transmission rate, which involves the amount of data transferred by each sensor node to the coordinating node, while the number of sensor nodes in the network increases, it can be calculated from the equation described earlier for the maximum transmission rate of a sensor node. It should be noted that the payload must be fully loaded before each transmission.

Therefore, the choice of the star-type architecture with the coordinating node defined by a smartphone and the three sensor nodes characterized by the left insole, right insole and electrostimulator appears to be sound and coherent with the project; this is due to its wide-spread use in healthcare applications (confirm) and the fact that only bidirectional communication is required between the sensor nodes and the defined coordinating node. With regard to latency time, the maximum throughput of a sensor node and the maximum throughput of the network, it is still necessary to apply the methodology described for the calculations, which is only possible with the physical presence of the components and the network architecture.

B. WiFi connection

The ESP32 device has, in addition to the conventional characteristics of a microcontroller, the ability to connect WiFi and bluetooth network. For these reasons, this device was chosen to compose the conception responsible for the monitoring of individuals with diabetic neuropathy, performing a fundamental role in the context of all wireless communication that surrounds

the project.

This microcontroller is capable of both connecting to existing WiFi networks and creating its own network. In this sense, to create a communication with a desired network, it is necessary to assign a proper programming on the device, from a software such as the Arduino IDE, which is widely used for this function; thus, it is appropriate to discuss the programming logic involved in this process. First, it is necessary to elucidate that the commands directed to the microcontroller, that is, that will be executed by the serial, have the prefix "Serial.", followed by the command itself – An example is the Serial.println() command, which prints the desired content on the software monitor, representing the microcontroller. In this bias, firstly, outside the setup and loop areas, one must include the WiFi.h library, which provides all the necessary resources for the connection, and create a constant to save the WiFi network name (ssid) and your password. After that, it is necessary to include the following elements: within the void setup() function, one must use Serial.begin(), to initiate communication between the software and the microcontroller with the transmission rate determined within the parenthesis of the command; WiFi.begin() with the two parameters filled respectively with the constant name and password of the network, to perform the first command of WiFi, asking connection to the network; create a small loop that will run until the network connection is made, which works by comparing the connection status: while(WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED){ Serial.print(".");}. In this way, the connection to the desired network will be established.

An application of great importance made possible by the connection of the microcontroller in a network is the ability to transmit a data by WiFi using the ESP32. This task can be performed by creating a webserver, which is, in a simplified way, a server that communicates through the HTTP protocol – standard used for communications of the type server-client.

The IP (Internet Protocol) is a sequence of numbers that configures an identification, being generated by a network and assigned to each device connected to it. In this context, the creation of a server and client system – performed by the microcontroller and the browser, respectively – can be accomplished by taking the IP of the microcontroller followed by its insertion into a browser; the action to get this identification for the device connected to the network is performed by the Serial.println(WiFi.localIP()) command. These simple steps create the client and server organization, and a page in the browser with the IP address is generated to perform the tasks and applications desired by the user, being able to make requests, exchange data and receive commands from the server; to develop the content of the browser page, the html language can be used, and bidirectional actions between server and client are carried out using the HTTP and WiFi protocols.

Secondly, it is essential to address the commands that effectively allow data and commands to be sent and received between client and server. In this sense, it is important to make HTTP requests using commands such as "Get" and "Post", linked to the appropriate formatting, using their respective headers, status and content, which allow the elements involved to interpret that this is information that follows the HTTP standard; it should be noted that it is possible to send data in raw form using "Client.print" in conjunction with the desired HTML programming. From the communication and exchange of information made possible by these commands, countless applications can be developed.

In addition to the ability to connect to an existing WiFi network from the previously explained method, the ESP32 allows the creation of such a network – this function represents is of great importance, in view of the wide

applicability and practicality that it offers, by not requiring the presence and connection of pre-existing networks, being able to establish a connection between devices in the desired way and on its own. In this bias, the methodology responsible for the generation of a WiFi network by the microcontroller consists, firstly, to define constants to store the name and password of the network that will be created; secondly, one must use the command "WiFi.softAP()" filled with the parameters name and password of the network; thus, the WiFi network will be created and the connection of other devices of it can be effected by printing the IP of the access point on the serial monitor and using it.

An application was made that dates back to the transfer of data via WiFi by ESP32 from the creation of a webserver, using all the concepts previously addressed, as well as basic knowledge related to the programming logic linked to the microcontroller, which involve the commands "Serial.begin()" with the desired transmission rate as a parameter, to initiate serial communication; "pinMode()" to place a particular ESP32 pin as a data input or output, analog or digital; "analogRead()" to read the analog input from a pin; "digitalRead()" to read the digital input from a pin; "digitalWrite()" to place high or low logical level on a pin configured as digital output. A simple task was chosen in order to demonstrate the sending and receiving of information by the microcontroller in a WiFi network.

For this, a conjuncture of a circuit was implemented in a protoboard – formed by a potentiometer and a resistor – and a program in the Arduino IDE, which basically makes an analog value of the resistance of a resistor be controlled by a potentiometer and read by ESP32 (generates and stores a digital value in the range from 0 to 4095); This value is sent to the created webserver (Figure 2), which ascends the ESP32 led (Figure 3) if the digital value of the microcontroller corresponding to the analog value of the resistance is in the range of 1/4 to 2/4 (greater than 1023 and less than or equal to 2047). In this way, in the first place, the microcontroller was connected to the network provided by a smartphone; after that, the microcontroller's IP has been set (Figure 3) and pasted it into a browser, creating the server-client system; then it is already possible to carry out the desired application.

Fig. 2: Webserver created

Fig. 3: Getting the IP for communication

In this way, structuring the network based on a Wi-Fi connection is a good alternative to the equipment, in view of the aspects discussed above; its implementation has been developed to the point presented, and the current phase of work in this area consists of connecting the three sensor nodes to the coordinator node simultaneously, in order to transmit data packets and bidirectional commands between the different types of nodes in real time.

C. Data transmission

A fundamental aspect of all wireless communication that will underpin the targeted equipment refers to data transmission. It allows the sharing of information between microcontrollers and smartphone, thus enabling the sending and receiving of data and commands between the sensor nodes and the coordinator node. In this transfer, the information components are data packets.

A data packet is a segment of a larger message composed of bits - small units of information, transmitted in the form of electrical pulses for interpretation by target devices. It optimizes the sharing of information and enables the connection between more than two devices simultaneously, since there is a packet switching, in which these segments can travel over the same transmission medium and in any order; these packets are recombined into the original message as soon as they are received by the device.

The effective transmission of data packets between sensor nodes and the coordinator node can be performed through programming, which has the setup and loop base previously described, necessary for connecting to the desired WiFi network and creating server-client communication through WebServer. In addition, the logic consists of creating a vector of the required size to store the bits to be transmitted, in addition to using commands for reading and transmission which, in the case of the application, will be the "analogRead" for the interpretation of the signals received by the sensor nodes, and the "client.print" to send this data to the coordinator node.

In this way, for the application of the equipment aimed by this work, it is necessary that the transmission of the packets occurs continuously over time, spaced by the period to be determined; for this, it is possible to use the "delay" command, which has as parameter the waiting time in milliseconds to continue the execution of the next commands, within a loop to fill a vector with the information read and transmit it to the desired destination. However, to solve the issue of waiting time for execution of new transmissions, it is also possible to use the timer method, with the "TimerOne" library, in which a function is created that will be called once or continuously when a certain period passes.

In order to demonstrate an application related to the context previously worked, a data transmission system was developed, in which a 10-bit data packet containing values read from a potentiometer is transmitted from the client to the server (from a Webserver complex) every 100 milliseconds (mS). This program followed the guide-lines already described for the establishment of the WiFi connection and creation of the Webserver, in addition to the logic responsible for carrying out the data transmission.

Fig. 4: transmission of the data package every 100mS

Data transmission was effectively carried out using the proposed application, in which a 10-byte data packet was transmitted continuously between server and client, using the methodology described previously; the next stage consists of working on the part related to processing and handling this data.

III. Conclusions

The great lack of resources and treatments for individuals with diabetic neuropathy show the need to create new mechanisms to control and treat the symptoms caused by the disease.

In this sense, the project that consists of the development of a system for monitoring the condition of the lower limbs of the users is established as an important alternative for coping of the disease. The segment of this conception treated in this work is shown as fundamental, because it underpins all communication between the components of the project.

The proposition of the architecture is presented as a possible alternative to compose the project, because it is viable and effective; the communication via WiFi was successfully established and represents a great possibility, given its high capacity and practicality, and the next phase of the application in this context is under development; the suggested methodology for data transmission is promising, but further testing is still needed to verify its applicability and effectiveness.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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